

ENHANCING THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN INCREASING THE ACCESSIBILITY OF BANKING SERVICES

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Abstract. This article comprehensively analyzes the role and importance of digital transformation in increasing the popularity of banking services. In the current conditions of globalization and the digital economy, the introduction of innovative technologies in the banking system allows you to improve the quality of customer service, simplify the use of services, and save time and costs. The article also analyzes the problems arising in the process of digital transformation, including factors such as information security, lack of technological infrastructure, and the level of digital literacy of the population.

Keywords: digital transformation, banking services, internet banking, mobile banking, financial technologies (FinTech), artificial intelligence, digital economy.

Currently, digital transformation processes in the global economy are deeply penetrating the banking and financial system, along with all other sectors. In particular, the use of modern information and communication technologies in the provision of banking services is becoming an important factor in creating convenience for customers, increasing the speed of services, and ensuring their popularity. As a result of the formation of the digital economy, traditional banking services are increasingly being replaced by remote and automated services.

undergoing large-scale reforms to modernize and digitize the banking system. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079 dated October 5, 2020 on approval of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy is one of the important documents aimed at accelerating digital transformation in the country, including the introduction of modern services in the banking and financial sector [1]. This strategy sets as a priority task increasing the quality and popularity of services through the widespread introduction of digital technologies in all sectors of the economy, in particular in the banking sector. In addition, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-580 dated November 5, 2019 "On Banks and Banking Activities" specifically emphasizes the need to use modern technologies in the provision of banking services, and to provide customers with convenient and secure services [2]. This law establishes the basic principles of the activities of banks and serves to support their innovative development. At the same time, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-578 dated 01.11.2019 "On Payments and Payment Systems" creates a legal basis for increasing the popularity of banking services by developing electronic payment systems, expanding remote banking services, and encouraging cashless payments [3].

Digital transformation is expanding the scope of banking services and bringing them to a new level in terms of quality. In particular, internet banking, mobile banking, QR payments, e-wallets, and artificial intelligence-based services allow customers to be served 24/7 [4]. This significantly increases the level of use of banking services. According to statistics, in recent years, the number of users of remote banking services in Uzbekistan has increased several

times, which clearly demonstrates the practical effectiveness of digital transformation. Also, the regulatory and legal documents adopted by the Central Bank are accelerating the process of digitization of banking services. In particular, the norms defining the procedures for remote identification, electronic contracts and the provision of digital services are aimed at simplifying the activities of banks and creating favorable conditions for customers. However, there are a number of problems in the process of digital transformation. In particular, ensuring information security, combating cyber threats, increasing the digital literacy of the population and developing technological infrastructure remain urgent issues. In particular, the lack of Internet speed and quality in some regions, as well as the ability to use modern devices, hinder the full popularity of banking services.

Digital transformation processes are becoming one of the decisive factors in increasing the popularity of banking services [5]. In particular, internet banking, mobile applications, artificial intelligence (AI), and automated services are increasing the efficiency of the banking system and leading to a sharp increase in the number of customers. Modern research shows that the use of banking services has increased significantly globally as a result of the introduction of digital technologies.

Internet banking services are one of the first and most important steps in increasing the popularity of banking services. According to statistics, by 2026, the number of Internet banking users worldwide will exceed 4.2 billion, which is about 53% of the global population [6]. This indicator clearly shows that banking services have moved from a traditional form to a digital one. Also, the fact that 71% of banking transactions are carried out through digital channels confirms the widespread popularity of Internet banking services. Internet banking is increasing the need for banking services by allowing customers to remotely manage their accounts, make payments and transfer funds. According to research, 73.2% of users check their account balance via Internet banking, and 69.2% use it to transfer funds [7]. This shows that this type of service has dramatically increased the importance of banking services in everyday life.

Mobile banking services have taken the popularity of banking services to a new level. Today, the majority of users use banking services via mobile devices. According to data, more than 2.17 billion users globally use mobile banking services. In addition, 72% of bank customers have chosen mobile applications as their main banking tool. Providing services through mobile applications has formed a "mobile-first" approach in the banking system. For example, in the United States, more than 60% of all banking transactions are carried out via mobile devices. Also, the fact that 70.8% of users access their bank accounts via smartphones indicates the superiority of mobile banking services. As a result, many customers have stopped visiting traditional bank branches: in some countries, 39% of customers use mobile banking services exclusively.

Artificial intelligence technologies are serving as an innovative tool in increasing the popularity of banking services. AI-based services, in particular, chatbots, automated advisory systems and fraud detection systems, are making banking services more convenient and secure. According to statistics, by 2025, 90% of financial institutions will use artificial intelligence to detect and monitor fraud. In addition, the quality of customer service in banks that have implemented AI technologies has improved by 46%. Artificial intelligence provides an individual approach to customers and allows them to offer services tailored to their needs. This increases customer trust in banking services and encourages them to use them more widely.

Automated banking services are also having a significant impact on the popularity of banking services . For example, automatic payment systems, digital lending and biometric authentication systems make using services fast and easy. According to research, 64.2 percent of mobile banking users use biometric authentication. This not only increases the security of services, but also simplifies their use. Automated services also play a significant role in reducing banking costs. Banks that have implemented AI and automation have seen operational costs drop by 20-40 percent. This allows banks to offer services more cost-effectively and to a wider audience.

Internet banking, mobile applications, artificial intelligence and automated services are emerging as interrelated and complementary factors in increasing the popularity of banking services. These technologies not only increase the convenience of banking services, but also ensure their speed, security and reliability. As a result, the number of users of banking services is increasing, and financial services are reaching a wider audience.

Although digital transformation processes are playing an important role in the development of banking services , there are also a number of systemic problems associated with this process. In particular, information security, lack of technological infrastructure, and the level of digital literacy of the population are the main factors hindering the full availability of banking services .

First, the issue of information security is one of the most pressing issues in digital banking. As a result of the digitization of banking services, a large amount of financial and personal information is stored electronically. This increases the risk of cyberattacks, fraud and data leaks. In recent years, the number of cybercrimes has increased significantly worldwide . In particular, phishing attacks, malware and identity theft pose a serious threat to bank customers. Therefore, banks are required to implement modern protection systems, including biometric authentication, two-factor authentication (2FA) and artificial intelligence-based monitoring systems. However, these measures may not always be effective enough , as cyber threats are constantly evolving.

Secondly, the insufficient development of technological infrastructure is also a significant problem. High-speed internet, modern server systems and stable technological platforms are necessary for the effective use of digital banking services. However, in some regions, poor internet quality, communication interruptions and Lack of technical means limits the full use of digital services. In particular, the level of use of banking services by the population living in rural areas is significantly lower than in urban areas. This leads to a decrease in the level of financial inclusion. At the same time, the fact that banks themselves are sometimes using outdated technological systems slows down the digital transformation process.

Third, the level of digital literacy of the population is also important. To effectively use digital banking services, users need to have a certain level of technological knowledge and skills. However, some segments of the population, especially the elderly and those living in rural areas, do not have sufficient digital literacy. As a result, they face difficulties in using mobile applications, internet banking or electronic payment systems. This is a significant factor limiting the popularity of banking services. Low digital literacy is also contributing to the increase in cyber fraud . Users may suffer financial losses as a result of trusting phishing messages or not following the rules for protecting their personal data. Therefore, it is important

for banks and government agencies to expand promotional activities, trainings and educational programs aimed at increasing the digital literacy of the population.

To overcome the above problems, a comprehensive approach is necessary. In particular, systematic measures should be taken to strengthen information security, develop modern technological infrastructure, and increase the digital literacy of the population. Only then can digital transformation processes be fully effective in increasing the popularity of banking services.

In conclusion, digital transformation is playing a crucial role in increasing the popularity of banking services. The introduction of Internet banking, mobile applications, artificial intelligence and automated services is ensuring the convenience, speed and openness of banking services, attracting a wide range of population to the financial system. As a result, the level of use of banking services is increasing and financial inclusion is expanding. At the same time, issues such as ensuring information security, developing technological infrastructure, and increasing the digital literacy of the population remain relevant in the process of digital transformation. These issues, if not addressed in a timely and effective manner, could hinder the widespread adoption of digital services

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